

A Novel Approach to the Synthesis of (+)Serricornin and (+)Anhydroserricornin, the Sex Pheromone of the Cigarette Beetle

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(±)Serricornin (**1**) and (±)anhydroserricornin (**14**) have been synthesised in ten steps by a novel approach starting from benzonorbornadiene (**2**).

SERRICORNIN (**1**) is the sex pheromone of cigarette beetle (*Lasioderma serricorne* F.) which is the major pest of cured tobacco leaves^{1,2}. The absolute stereochemistry of natural stereoisomer of serricornin (**1**), has been established by Mori *et al.*^{3,4} as 4*S*, 6*S*, 7*S*. Due to lability of **1**, identification and comparison of samples were performed

with the acetate (**1a**). Because of the practical value of serricornin, its synthesis has attracted much attention⁵⁻⁷. The anhydroserricornin (**14**) which has been identified⁸ as the second pheromone of this species is significantly more active than **1** and its synthesis has been published⁶. In this paper we report a conceptually novel approach to the synthesis of (±)serricornin acetate (**1a**) and (±)anhydroserricornin (**14**).

The synthetic strategy which culminated in the synthesis of **1a** is presented in Scheme 1. The first phase of the work was the synthesis of the key intermediate 1,3-dimethylindane (**5**). The methods reported in the literature are rather circuitous⁹ or suffer from low yields¹⁰. In the present approach, readily available benzonorbornadiene (**2**)¹¹ was subjected to ozonolysis in dichloromethane at -78° , followed by reduction with excess sodium borohydride in 50% aqueous ethanol to afford 1,3-bis(hydroxymethyl)indane (**3**) in 70% yield. Treatment of the diol (**3**) with two equivalents of methanesulphonyl chloride and triethylamine in dichloromethane at -20° yielded the dimesylate (**4**; 95%) which on reduction with eight equivalents of lithium aluminium hydride in ether for 2 h gave 1,3-dimethylindane⁵ (**5**; 80%) in very good yield.

Having introduced two stereocenters in the molecular skeleton, the next phase of the synthesis was directed towards the conversion of **5** to the

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) O₃, CH₂Cl₂, -78° , (ii) NaBH₄, EtOH-H₂O, (iii) OH₂SO₂Cl, Et₃N, CH₂Cl₂, -20° , (iv) LiAlH₄, Et₂O; (v) Li, NH₃, EtOH-THF, -83° , (vi) OsO₄, N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide, acetone-water, (vii) Pb(OAc)₄, benzene, 25° , (viii) Ag₂O, DMAP, CH₂Cl₂, (ix) DBU, benzene, 35° , (x) PTS/benzene, 50° .

cyclopentene (**11**). Birch reduction of **5** with ten equivalents of lithium in liquid ammonia followed by six equivalents of ethanol gave the dihydro compound (**6**; 95%). Exposure of the diene (**6**) to Johnson-Lemieux reaction conditions¹² using osmium tetroxide and sodium metaperiodate led

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to a mixture of products. However, catalytic osmylation procedure¹³ using 0.1 equivalent of osmium tetroxide and 1.3 equivalents of *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide in aqueous acetone for 80 h resulted in the formation of the diol (7; 25%). This is curiously an incomplete reaction with recovery of more than 60% of starting material which can be recycled. Clearly osmium is being removed from its catalytic cycle by some process. It is possible that osmium is forming a complex with the diene (6) which is not readily cleaved by *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide. Several other hydroxylation procedures were attempted without much success¹⁴. Nevertheless further work on the synthesis was pursued with the diol (7) obtained by catalytic osmylation, followed by recycling of the recovered starting material. Oxidation of 7 with lead tetraacetate (1.7 equiv.) in benzene at room temperature gave the dialdehyde (8) which was immediately reduced with sodium borohydride in ethanol at 0° to yield the diol (9; 95%). Formation of the dimesylate (10) with methane sulphonyl chloride and triethylamine and reduction with lithium aluminium hydride yielded the desired hydrocarbon (11; 60%).

The final phase of the synthesis would then involve an oxidative cleavage of the double bond in the cyclic precursor (11) to furnish the desired acyclic molecular framework of serricornin. Ozonolysis of the hydrocarbon (11) in dichloromethane at 0° followed by reduction of the ozonide with sodium borohydride in ethanol afforded the hemiacetal (12; 92%) as the only product. Acetylation of 12 with acetic anhydride and 4-dimethylaminopyridine gave the acetate (13; 63%). Treatment of 13 with DBU in benzene afforded serricornin acetate as mixture of epimers at C-4. It has earlier been demonstrated that natural serricornin is readily epimerised at C-4³. Treatment of 12 with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid in benzene gave anhydroserricornin (14; 54%)⁵. The spectral data of the synthetic pheromones were closely similar to those reported for the natural pheromone⁵⁻⁷.

In conclusion, we have been able to demonstrate the strategy of acyclic stereoselection from cyclic precursors to the synthesis of (±)serricornin (1) and (±)anhydroserricornin (14).

Experimental

All b.ps. and m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were measured on Perkin-Elmer 377 and 580 spectrometers. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on Varian HA-100 (100 MHz) and Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as internal standard. Kiesselgel 60 (particle size 0.063–0.200 mm; Merck) was used for SiO₂ column chromatography.

Synthesis of diol 2: Ozone gas was bubbled through a solution of benzonorbornadiene (2; 14.2 g, 100 mmol) dissolved in dry dichloromethane

(200 ml) at about –78° for 1 h. The reaction was followed by the disappearance of the starting material through tlc analysis. A solution of sodium borohydride (30.4 g, 800 mmol) dissolved in cold 50% aqueous ethanol (200 ml) was added slowly to the stirred ozonide mixture, while the temperature was maintained at about 25° by occasional ice-bath cooling. The reaction mixture was warmed up in a water-bath for 2 h with stirring and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The mixture was acidified with acetic acid and extracted with ethyl acetate (4 × 200 ml). The organic extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (100 ml) followed by brine (100 ml) and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The solution was filtered and concentrated to afford a thick oil which was crystallised from ethyl acetate–hexane (1:1) to furnish 2 (12.7 g, 70%) as a white solid m.p. 99–100° (Found: C, 74.30; H, 7.70. C₁₁H₁₄O₂ calcd. for: C, 74.15; H, 7.86%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 290 cm⁻¹; δ 2.18 (2H, s), 2.44–2.72 (2H, m), 3.44 (2H, m), 3.92 (4H, d) and 7.3 (4H, s); m/e 178 (M⁺), 161, 148, 130, 129, 117, 103, 91 and 77.

Synthesis of dimesylate 3: To a solution of 2 (5.34 g, 30 mmol) and triethylamine (6.6 g, 66 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (70 ml) was added slowly methanesulphonyl chloride (6.84 g, 60 mmol) dropwise over 0.5 h at about –20°. The resulting mixture was stirred for 6 h at –20°. The reaction mixture was transferred to a separatory funnel with the aid of more dichloromethane and was first washed with ice-water (50 ml) followed by cold 10% hydrochloric acid (50 ml), saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (50 ml) and brine (50 ml). The organic extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate followed by evaporation of solvent under reduced pressure, affording the dimesylate (4; 9.5 g, 95%) which was recrystallised from dichloromethane–hexane (1:1), m.p. 134–35° (Found: C, 46.59; H, 5.29. C₁₄H₁₈O₆S₂ calcd. for: C, 46.71; H, 5.39%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 360, 1 350, 1 170 and 1 160 cm⁻¹; δ 1.8–2.3 (2H, m), 3.0 (6H, s), 3.65 (2H, m), 4.4 (4H, m) and 7.34 (4H, m); m/e 238 (M⁺ – CH₃SO₃H), 142, 129, 115, 102, 91, 79 and 63.

Hydrogenolysis of 4 with lithium aluminium hydride: To a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (8.2 g, 216 mmol) in absolute ether (250 ml) was added with efficient stirring the dimesylate (4) in several portions (9.02 g, 27 mmol). The resulting mixture was refluxed for 2 h, cooled and water was added slowly (8.2 ml) followed by 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (9.2 ml) and water (16.4 ml). The precipitated hydroxide was filtered through anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the filter cake was washed with ether (200 ml). The filtrate was evaporated to afford 5 (3.15 g, 80%) as a liquid, b.p. 80–2°/7 mm (lit¹⁰, b.p. 202–03°/740.5 mm); δ 1.3 (6H, d, *J* 7 Hz), 2.46 (2H, m) and 3.1 (2H, m).

Birch reduction of 5: Lithium pieces (4.6 g, 700 mmol) were added slowly to refluxing liquid

ammonia (400 ml) over 0.25 h. To the resulting blue solution, **5** (10.22 g, 70 mmol) was added in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (60 ml) and absolute ethanol (24 ml) slowly in about 0.3 h. The reaction mixture was mechanically stirred under reflux for 3 h. Solid ammonium chloride was added to destroy excess lithium and the reaction mixture left overnight to allow the ammonia to evaporate. Water (100 ml) was added to the crude mass and extracted with ether (4 × 100 ml). The ether extract was washed with water (2 × 100 ml) followed by brine (100 ml), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and concentrated to afford **6** (9.8 g, 95%) as an oil which was fractionated, b.p. 62–4°/7 mm (Found: C, 89.43; H, 10.75. $C_{11}H_{16}$ calcd. for: C, 89.19; H, 10.81%; $\nu_{\max}$ (thin film) 1640 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.0 (6H, d, J 6 Hz), 2.16–2.6 (8H, m) and 5.74 (2H, m); m/e 148 (M^+), 133, 132, 119, 118, 115, 107, 105, 93, 91, 77, 73, 65 and 55.

Cis-hydroxylation of 6 with osmium tetroxide: A solution of **6** (0.74 g, 5 mmol), *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide (0.995 g, 6.5 mmol) in acetone (25 ml) and distilled water (10 ml) was treated with a solution of osmium tetroxide (0.127 g in 6 ml of tetrahydrofuran, 0.5 mmol) and the resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 80 h. Ethyl acetate (50 ml) and saturated sodium bisulphite solution (5 ml) were added to it and the two-phase mixture was stirred vigorously for 0.25 h. The organic layer was removed and the aqueous phase extracted with ethyl acetate (4 × 40 ml). The combined organic layer was washed with saturated sodium chloride solution (50 ml), dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure to afford a green viscous liquid. The crude product from twelve such small-scale reactions was subjected to flash chromatography to yield the unchanged starting material **6** (5.4 g, 61%) (elution with petroleum ether) and the diol **7** (2.7 g, 25%) (elution with 4 : 1. ether–petroleum ether). The product obtained by column chromatography was recrystallised from ether–petroleum ether (3 : 2), m.p. 99–100° (Found: C, 72.65; H, 9.92. $C_{11}H_{18}O_2$ calcd. for: C, 72.52; H, 9.89%; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3330 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.98 (6H, d, J 6 Hz), 1.8–2.6 (8H, m) and 3.96 (2H, m); m/e 182 (M^+), 164, 149, 147, 131, 121, 120, 107, 105, 93 and 91.

Synthesis of diol 9: To a solution of the diol (**7**; 2.18 g, 12 mmol) in dry benzene (20 ml) was added lead tetraacetate (6.4 g, 14.4 mmol) in portions and the resulting mixture was stirred at room temperature for 0.3 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with anhydrous ether (50 ml) and filtered through a pad of celite and anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The filtrate upon concentration afforded the dialdehyde (**8**; 1.94 g) as a pale yellow oil which was immediately used in the next step.

The crude product from the above reaction was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml), and sodium borohydride (1.368 g, 36 mmol) was added at 0°. The

resulting mixture was stirred for 3 h at 0°. Crushed ice was added and the reaction mixture was allowed to warm up to room temperature and extracted with chloroform (4 × 50 ml). The organic layer was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a colourless oil which was crystallised (4 : 1. ether–petroleum ether) to afford **9** (1.87 g) as a solid, m.p. 59–60° (overall yield of 85%, from diol **7**) (Found: C, 71.68; H, 10.70. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2$ calcd. for: C, 71.73; H, 10.86%; $\nu_{\max}$ ($CHCl_3$) 3350 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.0 (6H, d, J 7 Hz), 2.04–2.8 (8H, m), 3.02 (2H, bs) and 3.54–3.8 (4H, m); m/e 184 (M^+), 166, 151, 139, 137, 135, 121, 120, 109, 107, 105, 95, 98, 91, 81, 79 and 77.

Synthesis of dimesylate 10: To a solution of **9** (1.8 g, 9.78 mmol) and triethylamine (2.17 g, 21.52 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran (20 ml) maintained at –20°, was added slowly methanesulphonyl chloride (2.22 g, 19.56 mmol) over 0.25 h. The resulting solution was stirred at –28° for an additional 2 h. The mixture was then transferred to a separatory funnel by means of dichloromethane, and washed successively with cold water (2 × 20 ml), cold 10% hydrochloric acid (20 ml), cold saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (20 ml) and brine (20 ml). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure to give a yellow liquid which was filtered through a short silica gel pad to yield the dimesylate (**10**; 3.03 g, 91%) (elution with 1 : 1. ether–petroleum ether) and used in the next step without further purification; $\nu_{\max}$ ($CHCl_3$) 1170 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.03 (6H, d), 2.1–2.8 (8H, m), 2.96 (6H, s) and 4.16 (4H, m).

Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of 10: To a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (2.58 g, 68 mmol) in anhydrous ether (100 ml) was added slowly the dimesylate (**10**; 2.89 g, 8.5 mmol) in ether (20 ml) and the resulting mixture refluxed for 2 h. Moist sodium sulphate was then added until no more gas evolved. The reaction mixture was filtered and the residue washed with ether several times. The filtrate was evaporated to afford an oil which was purified by flash column chromatography (elution with petroleum ether) to yield the hydrocarbon as an oil (**11**; 0.775 g, 60%) (Found: C, 86.97; H, 13.01. $C_{11}H_{20}$ calcd. for: C, 86.84; H, 13.16%; $\nu_{\max}$ ($CHCl_3$) 1620 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.91 (6H, t, J 7 Hz), 0.98 (6H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 1.82–2.38 (6H, m) and 2.58 (2H q, J 7 Hz); m/e 152 (M^+), 137, 123, 121, 119, 109, 107, 105, 96, 92 and 82.

Synthesis of hemiacetal 12: Ozone was bubbled through a solution of **11** (0.684 g, 4.5 mmol) in dichloromethane (15 ml) maintained at 0°. When tlc showed the disappearance of starting material (1 h) the dichloromethane was evaporated under reduced pressure. The ozonide was dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) and sodium borohydride (0.38 g, 10 mmol) was added in portions. The resulting mixture was stirred at 0° for 2 h. Acetic acid

(0.5 ml) was then added and stirred for 10 min. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with ether (3×30 ml). After washing with brine solution, it was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to yield an oil which was purified by flash chromatography to afford the hemiacetal (**12**; 0.778 g, 92%); $\nu_{\max}$ (CHCl₃) 3 370 cm⁻¹; δ 0.9–0.95 (6H, bt), 1.05–1.15 (6H, bd), 1.2–1.8 (8H, m), 1.9 (1H, bs) and 3.5–3.8 (1H, m).

Acetylation of 12 and epimerisation to 1a: A solution of the hemiacetal (**12**; 0.235 g, 1.75 mmol) in dichloromethane (5 ml) was treated with acetic anhydride (0.214 g, 2.1 mmol) and 4-dimethylaminopyridine (0.042 g, 0.35 mmol). The resulting solution was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. Methanol was then added (0.5 ml) and stirring continued for 0.25 h followed by addition of water (15 ml). The organic layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (3×20 ml). The ether extract was washed with brine, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, filtered and evaporated to yield the keto acetate as an oil (**13**; 0.256 g). The crude **13** was dissolved in dry benzene (5 ml), and DBU (0.1 ml) added and then stirred 25° overnight. The reaction mixture was diluted with ether (15 ml) and then washed successively with water, dilute HCl and water. After drying over MgSO₄ the solvent was evaporated and the residue purified by flash chromatography to yield the serricornin acetate (**1a**; 0.173 g, 95%) as an oil (elution with 1:1 ether–petroleum ether); $\nu_{\max}$ (CHCl₃) 1 730 and 1 705 cm⁻¹; δ 0.85 (6H, t, *J* 6 Hz), 1.03 (6H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 1.4–1.70 (5H, m), 2.0 (3H, s), 2.3–2.7 (3H, m) and 4.72 (1H, m); *m/e* 168 (*M*⁺–CH₃COOH), 139, 127, 111, 99, 86, 83, 57 and 29; ¹³C nmr δ 7.84, 10.11, 14.50, 16.67, 17.30, 21.02, 24.36, 33.80, 34.29, 35.78, 36.61, 43.49, 43.30, 78.11, 171.0 and 214.71.

(±)Anhydro-serricornin (**14**)^a: To a solution of **12** (0.114 g, 0.5 mmol) in benzene (6 ml) was added *p*-toluenesulphonic acid monohydrate (0.020 g, 0.1 mmol) and the mixture stirred at 25° for 2 h and then heated at 50° for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ether (15 ml) and washed successively with water, dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and brine. The organic extract was dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated to give an oil (0.065 g)

which was purified by flash chromatography on basic Al₂O₃ to afford (±)anhydro-serricornin (0.042 g, 50%); $\nu_{\max}$ (thin film) 1 700 and 1 600 cm⁻¹; δ 0.81–0.84 (3H, d), 0.90–1.00 (6H, t), 1.3–1.65 (3H, m), 1.60 (3H, s), 1.8–2.20 (4H, m) and 3.5–3.6 (1H, m); *m/e* 168 (*M*⁺).

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References

1. T. OHUMAN, M. KOHNO, K. KATO and M. NOGUCHI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, 2361.
2. T. OHUMAN, K. KATO and M. NOGUCHI, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1979, 43, 2005.
3. K. MORI, H. NOMI, T. OHUMAN, M. KOHNO, K. KATO and M. NOGUCHI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1981, 22, 1127.
4. K. MORI, H. NOMI, T. OHUMAN, M. KOHNO, K. KATO, and M. NOGUCHI, *Tetrahedron*, 1982, 38, 3705; M. MORI, T. OHUMAN, M. KOHNO, K. KATO, M. NOGUCHI, H. NOMI and K. MORI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 23, 667; M. MORI, T. OHUMAN, K. KATO and K. MORI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 23, 4593.
5. M. ONO, I. ONISHI, T. OHUMAN, M. KOHNO and K. KATO, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1980, 44, 2259; T. OHUMAN, M. KOHNO, K. KATO, M. NOGUCHI, H. NOMI and K. MORI, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1981, 45, 2019; R. BAKER and J. A. DEVLIN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1983, 147.
6. R. W. HOFFMANN, W. HELBIG and W. LADNER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 23, 3479.
7. P. A. BARTLETT, D. P. RICHARDSON and J. MYERSON, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, 40, 2317; T. FUJISAWA, K. TAJIMA and T. SATO, *Chem. Lett.*, 1984, 1669.
8. H. Z. LEVINSON, A. R. LEVINSON, W. FRANCKE, W. MACKENROTH and V. HERMANN, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1981, 68, 148.
9. P. A. PLATTNER, A. FURST and K. JIRASEK, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, 30, 1320.
10. S. S. HIRSCH and W. J. BAILEY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, 43, 4090.
11. L. FRIEDMAN and F. M. LOGOLLO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, 34, 3089.
12. R. PAPP0, D. S. ALLEN, JR, R. V. LEMIEUX and W. S. JOHNSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 478.
13. V. VAN RHRENNAN, R. O' KELLY and D. Y. CHA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, 4485.
14. T. OGINO and K. MOCHIZUKI, *Chem. Lett.*, 1979, 443; L. MANGONI, M. ADINOLFI, G. BARONE and M. FARRILLI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, 4485; V. BHUSHAN, R. RATHORE and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Synthesis*, 1984, 481.